

THE INFLUENCE OF BRAND IMAGE, TRUST, AND SERVICE QUALITY ON REVISIT INTENTION MEDIATED BY PATIENT SATISFACTION (CASE STUDY AT THE BHAYANGKARA HOSPITAL OF THE YOGYAKARTA SPECIAL REGION REGIONAL POLICE)

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Abstract

This study aims to analyze the influence of Brand Image, trust, and service quality on patients' revisit intention with patient satisfaction as a mediating variable at Bhayangkara Hospital, POLDA of the Special Region of Yogyakarta. The increasing competition among hospitals demands a comprehensive evaluation of the factors that shape patient loyalty. This research uses a quantitative approach with a survey method involving 250 patient respondents selected through purposive sampling. Data analysis was conducted using Partial Least Square (PLS) with SmartPLS 4 software. The findings show that Brand Image, trust, and service quality have a positive and significant effect on patient satisfaction and revisit intention. Patient satisfaction is also proven to mediate the relationship between the three independent variables and revisit intention, as indicated by p-values below 0.05. These results confirm that a positive hospital image, trust in the competence of medical staff, and superior service quality create a satisfying patient experience, thus encouraging revisit behavior. Theoretically, this study strengthens the conceptual model that satisfaction is a key element bridging patients' perceptions and loyalty in the healthcare sector. Practically, the findings provide implications for hospital management to enhance the synergy between image management, trust-building, and service quality improvement to create sustainable patient satisfaction and retention.

Keywords: *Brand Image, trust, service quality, patient satisfaction, revisit intention.*

INTRODUCTION

Patient behavior plays a crucial role in determining the effectiveness of healthcare systems, particularly in how patients interact with hospitals. In Indonesia, patient behavior is strongly influenced by social, cultural, and economic contexts, which shape expectations, experiences, and patterns of healthcare utilization. Understanding patient behavior is therefore essential for identifying challenges and opportunities in hospital service delivery and for developing sustainable healthcare strategies (Habib et al., 2025). One prominent manifestation of patient behavior in the healthcare sector is repeat hospital visits. Previous studies indicate that a significant proportion of patients, especially those with chronic conditions, tend to revisit hospitals within relatively short periods. Habib et al. (2025) report that 68.8% of chronic patients conduct multiple visits in close succession, while Helmy et al. (2025) observe a steady increase in outpatient visits in Indonesian hospitals. These findings suggest a strong dependency on hospitals for continuous healthcare needs and highlight the importance of retaining patients through consistent and high-quality services. Repeat visit behavior reflects patients' proactive efforts to seek clarity, continuity, and satisfactory outcomes from healthcare services. Dhewi et al. (2025) note that 62.5% of patients return because their previous healthcare needs were not fully met, while Wiogo (2025) finds that 57.9% revisit hospitals due to ongoing treatment or unresolved health conditions. Such behavior underscores the strategic importance of hospitals in meeting patient expectations and ensuring service consistency.

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Repeat visit intention represents the cognitive and emotional readiness of patients to return to the same hospital in the future. According to Arief et al. (2024), repeat visit intention is driven by trust and satisfaction formed through positive evaluations of previous service experiences. This intention becomes the foundation for long-term patient loyalty and sustained hospital performance. Preliminary survey results conducted at Bhayangkara POLDA Special Region of Yogyakarta Hospital indicate a strong tendency toward repeat visit intention. Most respondents consider the hospital their primary healthcare choice and express a clear intention to continue using its services. This reflects the hospital's success in meeting patient needs and delivering satisfactory healthcare experiences.

Table 1. Summary of Preliminary Survey on Repeat Visit Intention

Indicator of Repeat Visit Intention	Strongly Agree (%)	Agree (%)	Neutral (%)	Disagree (%)
Hospital as primary healthcare choice	69	22	6	3
Will continue using hospital services	61	25	11	3
Intention to revisit in the future	58	31	8	3

The high level of repeat visit intention is closely associated with several key factors, namely brand image, trust, service quality, and patient satisfaction. Brand image represents the collective perception of a hospital's reputation, credibility, and identity. A strong brand image enhances emotional attachment and trust, which in turn encourages patients to revisit the hospital (Tanner & Kristaung, 2024; Jak et al., 2024). Preliminary findings show that Bhayangkara Hospital is widely perceived as reputable and positively regarded by patients. Trust further strengthens patients' willingness to return, as it reflects confidence in the hospital's competence, integrity, and commitment to patient well-being. High trust levels observed in the preliminary survey indicate that patients feel secure and confident in the care provided. In addition, service quality particularly responsiveness, empathy, reliability, and staff competence significantly influences patient satisfaction and repeat visit intention (Hai et al., 2021).

Patient satisfaction emerges as a critical mediating variable that transforms perceptions of brand image, trust, and service quality into actual repeat visit intention. Satisfied patients are more likely to return, remain loyal, and recommend the hospital to others. Previous studies confirm that satisfaction acts as a bridge linking service-related factors to behavioral intentions (Yuniarti & Hidayat, 2021; Putra et al., 2024). Despite extensive research on these variables, studies that comprehensively integrate brand image, trust, service quality, patient satisfaction, and repeat visit intention particularly within the Indonesian hospital context remain limited. This study addresses this research gap by examining the mediating role of patient satisfaction in strengthening the relationship between brand image, trust, service quality, and repeat visit intention at Bhayangkara POLDA Special Region of Yogyakarta Hospital. The findings are expected to provide evidence-based insights for hospital management in developing effective patient retention strategies and enhancing long-term competitiveness.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Brand Image

In the hospital context, brand image is defined as the perception formed by patients based on their experiences, interactions, and overall impressions of the hospital. Damayanthie et al. (2024) state that hospital brand image encompasses patients' beliefs, emotions, knowledge, and impressions acquired through interactions with healthcare services. This intangible asset is highly important in encouraging patient loyalty and repeat visit intention. Rahman and Desembrianita (2023) describe hospital brand image as a multifaceted evaluative construct shaped by patient perceptions, including functional attributes such as facilities and symbolic values such as empathy and prestige. Indriani et al. (2024) emphasize that brand image extends beyond logos or visual identity, encompassing emotional relationships, credibility, and professional competence.

The manifestation of hospital brand image is multidimensional, incorporating functional elements such as service quality, facilities, and staff expertise (Rahman & Desembrianita, 2023). In addition, emotional components such as trust, prestige, and relational bonds play a significant role. Indriani et al. (2024) argue that brand image is built through consistent service delivery, clear communication, and a positive reputation. Irhamni et al. (2023) further explain that brand image develops gradually through patient experiences, involving aspects such as credibility and emotional attachment. B. T. Purwanto et al. (2022) suggest that the process of brand image formation involves both cognitive and emotional processes influenced by visual identity, public relations, and patient interactions. Hospital brand image plays a crucial role in enhancing patient trust, satisfaction, and loyalty. A strong brand image functions as a competitive differentiator in the healthcare market by facilitating patient retention and satisfaction (Damayanthie et al., 2024). Irhamni et al. (2023) highlight that a positive brand image fosters long-term relationships, creating an

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environment in which patients feel valued and secure. Furthermore, Indriani et al. (2024) reveal that a strong brand image influences decision-making, including patients' willingness to return and recommend the hospital to others. Research by B. T. Purwanto et al. (2022) demonstrates that brand image plays a strategic role in building trust, which ultimately contributes to higher repeat visit intention.

Trust

Trust in hospitals, as explained in various studies, centers on patients' willingness to rely on healthcare providers and institutions with the belief that they will act in the patients' best interests (Hutagaol et al., 2024). Trust is a multidimensional concept that involves both logical beliefs based on tangible service outcomes and emotional bonds formed through personal experiences. This definition encompasses interpersonal trust between patients and medical staff, as well as institutional trust related to the hospital's reputation and compliance with service standards (Habib et al., 2025; Marchama et al., 2025). In addition, relational aspects such as transparency, professionalism, and empathy further strengthen trust (Zahra et al., 2023). Trust functions as a psychological assurance for patients, providing confidence that their healthcare needs will be met effectively and ethically (Soulisa & Hidayat, 2022). Forms of trust in hospitals can be classified into interpersonal trust and institutional trust. Interpersonal trust is rooted in the relationship between patients and healthcare professionals, characterized by consistent behavior, clear communication, and ethical practices demonstrated by physicians and staff (Hutagaol et al., 2024; Marchama et al., 2025). In contrast, institutional trust is broader and relates to the hospital's ability to maintain its reputation and deliver high-quality care through reliable systems and protocols (Habib et al., 2025). Trust is manifested through relational dynamics, whereby ongoing positive interactions and experiences strengthen the bond between patients and the institution (Zahra et al., 2023). This can also be observed in patients' willingness to follow medical advice or recommend the hospital to others, reflecting confidence in both individual healthcare providers and the hospital's infrastructure (Soulisa & Hidayat, 2022).

Trust plays a critical role in shaping patient behavior and outcomes, profoundly influencing satisfaction and loyalty toward healthcare providers (Hutagaol et al., 2024). Trust determines whether patients choose to utilize services, adhere to medical recommendations, and return to the hospital for future care (Zahra et al., 2023). It serves as the foundation for building long-term relationships, fostering patient commitment, and ensuring sustained engagement with the healthcare system (Marchama et al., 2025). Furthermore, trust helps mitigate the information asymmetry faced by patients in medical contexts, providing reassurance and confidence in care-related decision-making despite limited medical knowledge (Soulisa & Hidayat, 2022). High levels of trust not only enhance the hospital's image but also improve perceptions of service quality, making trust a fundamental pillar of effective healthcare delivery (Habib et al., 2025). Overall, trust in hospitals reflects a combination of interpersonal and institutional dependence, shaped by the competence, integrity, and empathy of healthcare professionals, as well as strong and reliable institutional systems (Habib et al., 2025; Hutagaol et al., 2024). The importance of trust lies in its ability to enhance satisfaction, loyalty, and sustained engagement, ultimately bridging the gap between patient vulnerability and the complexity of healthcare systems (Soulisa & Hidayat, 2022). Therefore, trust is not merely a passive condition but an active and reciprocal dynamic that is essential for effective and ethical healthcare relationships (Marchama et al., 2025).

Service Quality

Service quality in hospitals is a multifaceted construct that reflects patients' evaluations of the overall excellence of both medical and non-medical services received. Siripipatthanakul (2021) defines service quality as the extent to which healthcare services meet or exceed patient expectations, adopting the five dimensions of the SERVQUAL model: tangibles, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy. Rahmawati et al. (2024) extend this definition by emphasizing the alignment between patient needs and service delivery, highlighting the critical role of interpersonal communication and emotional support in enhancing perceived service quality. Ananda (2024) integrates cultural sensitivity into this framework, proposing that culturally adapted care and communication styles significantly influence patient experiences. Jalil and Aida (2022) add that this concept lies in the gap between patient expectations and actual experiences, thereby underscoring the dynamic and patient-centered nature of service quality in hospitals. Forms of service quality in hospitals can be classified into tangible and intangible categories, reflecting the physical and experiential aspects of healthcare services. Tangible forms include infrastructure, medical equipment, cleanliness standards, and the aesthetic appeal of the hospital environment (Rahmawati et al., 2024; Siripipatthanakul, 2021). These physical attributes serve as indicators of professionalism and competence. However, intangible forms are equally important, encompassing a range of interpersonal and procedural dimensions. Jalil and

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Aida (2022) highlight aspects such as responsiveness, empathy, and administrative efficiency, which shape patient experiences throughout the care journey. Ananda (2024) emphasizes the importance of procedural clarity, such as ease of navigating hospital systems and the timeliness of medical interventions, as well as interpersonal factors such as cultural appropriateness in service delivery. Putra et al. (2024) identify two distinct forms of service quality: technical quality, which relates to diagnostic accuracy and treatment outcomes, and functional quality, which concerns how services are delivered, including healthcare providers' attitudes and communication styles. Collectively, these dimensions contribute to patients' holistic perceptions of service quality. The importance of service quality in hospitals lies in its profound impact on patient outcomes, satisfaction, and loyalty. High service quality enhances trust and confidence, which are essential factors in building long-term relationships with patients (Putra et al., 2024). Patient satisfaction is directly associated with perceived service quality, influencing the likelihood of patients returning to the facility and recommending it to others (Rahmawati et al., 2024). Jalil and Aida (2022) emphasize the role of empathy and responsiveness in meeting patient needs, which not only increases satisfaction but also contributes to better health outcomes by encouraging adherence to medical advice and treatment plans.

Ananda (2024) highlights the importance of integrating cultural sensitivity into services to address the needs of diverse patient populations, thereby enhancing accessibility and inclusivity. Moreover, service quality serves as a competitive differentiator in an increasingly saturated healthcare market, enabling hospitals to build strong reputations and secure patient loyalty. Its contribution to bridging the gap between perceived and expected service levels is crucial for sustaining healthcare systems that prioritize patient-centered care. Service quality in hospitals represents a complex interaction between tangible and intangible dimensions, extending beyond clinical effectiveness to include interpersonal, procedural, and environmental aspects. Based on frameworks such as SERVQUAL, service quality functions as a dynamic measure for evaluating the extent to which healthcare services align with patient expectations and experiences (Rahmawati et al., 2024; Siripipatthanakul, 2021). The integration of cultural sensitivity and a focus on emotional and procedural responsiveness underscore its evolving nature (Ananda, 2024; Jalil & Aida, 2022). Ultimately, service quality is not only central to patient satisfaction and loyalty but also to the broader goal of supporting sustainable, patient-centered healthcare systems

Patient Satisfaction

Patient satisfaction is an evaluative construct that reflects the extent to which healthcare service experiences meet patients' expectations. According to Sianita et al. (2024), patient satisfaction represents an assessment of expectation fulfillment based on the five SERVQUAL dimensions: tangible (physical environment and facilities), reliability (service dependability), responsiveness (staff promptness), assurance (staff competence and courtesy), and empathy (personalized attention to patients). This perspective is reinforced by Rifa and Bernarto (2023), who argue that satisfaction arises from the gap between patients' initial expectations and their actual service experiences, encompassing service quality, trust, and perceived value. Pranata et al. (2021) further expand this definition by viewing patient satisfaction as a subjective perception influenced by both clinical and non-clinical aspects, emphasizing its individual and contextual nature.

Patient satisfaction is multidimensional and reflects various aspects of the healthcare service experience. Angelica and Bernarto (2023) classify patient satisfaction using elements of the service marketing mix (7P), particularly people (staff competence and empathy), physical evidence (facility quality and cleanliness), process (efficiency and ease of service flow), and price (the balance between cost and perceived benefits). Pranata et al. (2021) identify satisfaction indicators including staff responsiveness, service speed, environmental comfort, and clarity of medical and administrative information. Park et al. (2021) emphasize psychosocial dimensions such as emotional comfort, sense of safety, continuity of care, and cultural sensitivity, particularly for diverse patient populations. In addition, Rifa and Bernarto (2023) highlight trust and feelings of being valued as tangible manifestations of satisfaction that shape patients' perceptions of overall service value.

The importance of patient satisfaction lies in its strategic impact on hospital sustainability and competitiveness. Satisfied patients tend to demonstrate higher loyalty, are more likely to return for future services, and willingly recommend hospitals to others, making satisfaction a key indicator of organizational success (Sianita et al., 2024). Rifa and Bernarto (2023) underscore that patient satisfaction directly influences behavioral intentions, including treatment adherence and recommendation intentions. Furthermore, Pranata et al. (2021) show that high satisfaction levels strengthen patient trust, which serves as the foundation for long-term relationships between patients and healthcare providers. Park et al. (2021) affirm that enhancing patient satisfaction supports the success of *patient-centered care* approaches by fostering open communication, emotional support, and trust-based

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relationships. Conceptually, patient satisfaction represents a comprehensive evaluation of healthcare service experiences encompassing physical, emotional, and perceived value dimensions throughout patient–hospital interactions. It reflects a balance between expectations and actual experiences shaped by service quality, empathy, and trust in healthcare providers (Angelica & Bernarto, 2023; Rifa & Bernarto, 2023). Therefore, patient satisfaction functions not only as a service performance indicator but also as a critical element in building patient loyalty, strengthening hospital reputation, and supporting sustainable, patient-oriented healthcare systems (Park et al., 2021; Sianita et al., 2024).

Revisit Intention

Revisit intention in the hospital context refers to patients' desire or tendency to return and use services at the same hospital in the future. According to Arief et al. (2024), revisit intention is associated with external factors that influence patients' decisions to return, reflecting patients' mental and emotional readiness to choose a particular hospital again based on prior experiences and interactions. Pighin et al. (2022) define revisit intention as a form of emotional commitment that emerges from positive patient experiences in hospitals. This intention develops when patients evaluate their satisfaction and trust in the services received, subsequently forming a desire to return. Such behavior is reflected in patients' repeated choices to visit the same healthcare provider. Syah and Suyitno (2025) further explain that revisit intention represents a patient tendency driven by feelings of comfort and satisfaction, whereby patients not only return but also express explicit preferences either verbally or in writing toward the hospital.

Hutagaol et al. (2024) describe revisit intention as a behavior that reflects patients' motivation and logical evaluation processes. This intention develops based on trust in the hospital's credibility and the extent to which the services provided align with patient expectations. Fairiska and Sulistiadi (2024) characterize revisit intention as part of the patient loyalty formation process, which begins with satisfaction, evolves into trust, and ultimately leads to the intention to return. Overall, revisit intention represents patients' psychological and behavioral tendencies to reuse hospital services based on previous interactions. This intention constitutes a deliberate decision grounded in emotional commitment, cognitive evaluation, and the gradual development of loyalty. From a behavioral perspective, revisit intention provides insight into patients' healthcare utilization patterns and serves as a key indicator for understanding loyalty toward a specific hospital.

METHOD

This study was conducted at Bhayangkara Hospital of the Special Region Police of Yogyakarta (POLDA DIY), located on Jalan Jogja–Solo KM.14, Kalasan, Sleman, Special Region of Yogyakarta. The hospital provides healthcare services for members of the Indonesian National Police, civil servants within the police institution and their families, as well as the general public. The study aims to examine patients' revisit intention by adopting a quantitative research approach using descriptive and verificative methods. A cross-sectional research design was employed to enable the measurement of relationships among Brand Image, trust, service quality, patient satisfaction, and revisit intention at a single point in time, thereby providing an empirical depiction of patients' perceptions and behavioral intentions based on their service experiences (Creswell & Creswell, 2023).

The data for this study were obtained from two primary sources: primary data and secondary data. Primary data were collected directly from respondents through a structured questionnaire designed to measure patients' perceptions of Brand Image, trust, service quality, patient satisfaction, and revisit intention. The questionnaire was distributed to patients who had previously utilized healthcare services at Bhayangkara Hospital POLDA DIY, ensuring that respondents possessed relevant and actual experience related to the research object. This approach allowed the researchers to obtain current and contextual data that accurately reflect real conditions within the hospital. Secondary data were obtained from supporting sources, including hospital annual reports, institutional documents, previous empirical studies, and relevant peer-reviewed journal articles. These data were used to provide theoretical context, support the analysis, and strengthen the interpretation of findings derived from the primary data.

The population of this study consisted of all patients who utilized healthcare services at Bhayangkara Hospital POLDA DIY during the period from January 2024 to December 2024. This population included patients with diverse demographic characteristics and types of medical services received, allowing for a comprehensive representation of patient experiences. The sample was selected as a subset of the population to serve as research respondents, with the objective of obtaining representative and generalizable findings. Purposive sampling was employed as the sampling technique to ensure that respondents had prior experience receiving services at the hospital and were willing to participate in the study. Respondents were selected based on specific criteria, such as the type of service received or the frequency of hospital visits, to ensure the relevance and accuracy of the collected data.

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The sample size was determined based on the number of indicators used in the research instrument. According to methodological guidelines, an adequate sample size for multivariate analysis ranges from five to ten times the number of indicators. Given that this study employed 27 indicators, the minimum required sample size was 135 respondents, while the maximum reference sample size was 270 respondents. This determination is consistent with the recommendations of Hair et al. (2019), which emphasize the importance of sufficient sample size to ensure the validity and reliability of multivariate statistical analyses. With the specified research design, data sources, sampling technique, and sample size, this study is expected to provide robust and comprehensive empirical evidence regarding the factors influencing patients' revisit intention at Bhayangkara Hospital POLDA DIY.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Validity Test

The validity test results indicate that for the Revisit Intention (Y) variable, one item (Y3) was found to be invalid, with a Corrected Item–Total Correlation value of 0.327, which was below the r-table value of 0.349; therefore, this item was removed in the first testing stage. In the second test, the remaining three items (Y1, Y2, and Y4) were confirmed to be valid, with higher correlation values ranging from 0.732 to 0.766. For Brand Image (X1), all seven items (X1.1–X1.7) were valid, with correlation values exceeding the r-table threshold (0.518–0.761). Similarly, all four items measuring Trust (X2) were valid, with correlation values ranging from 0.670 to 0.759. The Service Quality (X3) variable, consisting of 19 items (X3.1–X3.19), also demonstrated validity, with correlation values between 0.369 and 0.873, despite several items being close to the lower threshold. In addition, all seven items measuring Patient Satisfaction (Z) were valid, with correlation values ranging from 0.717 to 0.850. Overall, the results confirm that all measurement items used in this study are valid and suitable for further analysis, except for one revisit intention item (Y3) that was excluded during the initial validity testing.

Reliability Test

Table 2. Reliability Test Results

Variable	Number of Items	Cronbach's Alpha	Interpretation
Revisit Intention (Y) – Test I	4	0.771	Reliable
Revisit Intention (Y) – Test II	3	0.857	Reliable
Brand Image (X1)	7	0.857	Reliable
Trust (X2)	4	0.867	Reliable
Service Quality (X3)	19	0.926	Highly Reliable
Patient Satisfaction (Z)	7	0.932	Highly Reliable

All variables show Cronbach's Alpha values above 0.70, indicating good to excellent internal consistency. The reliability of Revisit Intention improved after the removal of the invalid item, while the remaining variables demonstrate strong and stable measurement reliability, confirming that the instruments are suitable for further analysis.

R-Square (R²) Values

Table 3. R-Square (R²) Values

Variable	R-Square	Adjusted R-Square
Patient Satisfaction (Z)	0.778	0.775
Revisit Intention (Y)	0.665	0.660

Based on Table 3, the R-square value for Patient Satisfaction (Z) is 0.778, with an adjusted R-square of 0.775, indicating that 77.8% of the variation in patient satisfaction can be explained by Brand Image, trust, and service quality. Meanwhile, the R-square value for Revisit Intention (Y) is 0.665, with an adjusted R-square of 0.660, suggesting that 66.5% of the variation in revisit intention is explained by patient satisfaction along with other independent variables. These results demonstrate that the structural model has strong explanatory power, indicating that the relationships among variables in this study are empirically capable of explaining patient behavior at Bhayangkara Hospital POLDA of the Special Region of Yogyakarta.

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Predictive Relevance (Q²)

Table 3. Predictive Relevance (Q²) Results

Variable	SSO	SSE	Q ² (= 1 – SSE/SSO)
Brand Image (X1)	1750.000	1750.000	–
Trust (X2)	1000.000	1000.000	–
Patient Satisfaction (Z)	1750.000	662.805	0.621
Service Quality (X3)	4750.000	4750.000	–
Revisit Intention (Y)	1000.000	449.755	0.550

Based on Table 3, the Q² value for Patient Satisfaction (Z) is 0.621 and for Revisit Intention (Y) is 0.550. Both values are greater than zero, indicating that the model has good predictive relevance. These results suggest that the structural model is able to predict more than 62% of the variance in patient satisfaction and 55% of the variance in revisit intention using the proposed constructs. Therefore, the model demonstrates strong predictive relevance and is suitable for examining causal relationships among variables in the context of patient behavior at Bhayangkara Hospital POLDA of the Special Region of Yogyakarta.

Effect Size F-Square (F²)

Table 4. Effect Size (F-square) Results

Variable	Brand Image (X1)	Trust (X2)	Patient Satisfaction (Z)	Service Quality (X3)	Revisit Intention (Y)
Brand Image (X1)	–	–	0.030	–	0.043
Trust (X2)	–	–	0.218	–	0.029
Patient Satisfaction (Z)	–	–	–	–	0.061
Service Quality (X3)	–	–	0.200	–	0.019
Revisit Intention (Y)	–	–	–	–	–

Based on Table 4, Trust (X2) has a moderate effect on Patient Satisfaction (Z) with an F-square value of 0.218, while Service Quality (X3) also shows a moderate effect with a value of 0.200. In contrast, Brand Image (X1) exhibits a small effect on patient satisfaction, with an F-square value of 0.030. Regarding Revisit Intention (Y), Brand Image (X1), Trust (X2), Service Quality (X3), and Patient Satisfaction (Z) each demonstrate small effect sizes, with F-square values ranging from 0.019 to 0.061. These findings indicate that trust and service quality are the most influential constructs in enhancing patient satisfaction, while the effects of other variables on revisit intention are relatively small but remain meaningful. Overall, the results highlight the importance of strengthening trust and service quality to improve patient satisfaction and foster patient loyalty at Bhayangkara Hospital POLDA of the Special Region of Yogyakarta.

Hypothesis Testing Results

Table 5. Direct Hypothesis Testing Results

Hypothesis	Path Relationship	Original Sample	T-Statistics	P-Values
H1	Brand Image (X1) → Patient Satisfaction (Z)	0.146	2.543	0.006
H2	Brand Image (X1) → Revisit Intention (Y)	0.217	3.007	0.001
H3	Trust (X2) → Patient Satisfaction (Z)	0.394	5.744	0.000
H4	Trust (X2) → Revisit Intention (Y)	0.195	1.770	0.039
H5	Patient Satisfaction (Z) → Revisit Intention (Y)	0.303	2.403	0.008
H6	Service Quality (X3) → Patient Satisfaction (Z)	0.403	7.461	0.000
H7	Service Quality (X3) → Revisit Intention (Y)	0.168	1.851	0.032

Based on the structural model evaluation using path coefficient analysis with the bootstrapping procedure, all proposed hypotheses were supported. Brand Image (X1) has a positive and significant effect on Revisit Intention (Y) (p = 0.001), indicating that a stronger hospital image increases patients' likelihood of returning. Similarly, Trust

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(X2) positively and significantly influences Revisit Intention (Y) ($p = 0.039$), suggesting that higher confidence in the hospital's reliability and professionalism encourages repeat visits. Service Quality (X3) also shows a positive and significant effect on Revisit Intention (Y) ($p = 0.032$), highlighting the importance of service performance in shaping patients' behavioral intentions. Furthermore, Patient Satisfaction (Z) has a positive and significant effect on Revisit Intention (Y) ($p = 0.008$), indicating that satisfied patients are more inclined to reuse hospital services. In addition, Brand Image (X1) significantly affects Patient Satisfaction (Z) ($p = 0.006$), implying that a positive institutional image enhances patients' overall satisfaction. Trust (X2) demonstrates a strong positive and significant influence on Patient Satisfaction (Z) ($p = 0.000$), reflecting the crucial role of credibility and integrity in shaping patient satisfaction. Lastly, Service Quality (X3) exerts the strongest positive and significant effect on Patient Satisfaction (Z) ($p = 0.000$), confirming that superior service delivery substantially increases patient satisfaction. Overall, these findings emphasize that brand image, trust, and service quality play significant roles in enhancing patient satisfaction and revisit intention, thereby reinforcing the importance of strengthening these factors to foster patient loyalty at Bhayangkara Hospital POLDA of the Special Region of Yogyakarta.

Table 6. Indirect Hypothesis Testing Results

Hypothesis	Path	Original Sample	T-Statistics	P-Values
H8	Brand Image (X1) → Patient Satisfaction (Z) → Visit Intention (Y)	0.044	1.875	0.031
H9	Trust (X2) → Patient Satisfaction (Z) → Visit Intention (Y)	0.119	1.811	0.035
H10	Service Quality (X3) → Patient Satisfaction (Z) → Visit Intention (Y)	0.122	2.581	0.005

The results indicate that patient satisfaction significantly mediates the relationship between brand image, trust, and service quality on visit intention. This shows that improvements in hospital image, trust, and service quality increase visit intention indirectly by enhancing patient satisfaction.

DISCUSSION

The Effect of Brand Image on Revisit Intention

The results of this study indicate that brand image has a positive and significant effect on patients' revisit intention. This finding suggests that a strong and favorable hospital image is able to shape positive perceptions regarding service quality, professionalism, and institutional credibility. When a hospital is perceived as reputable and trustworthy, patients tend to feel more confident in choosing the same hospital for future healthcare services. Furthermore, a positive brand image functions as an implicit assurance of service consistency. Positive experiences supported by a strong institutional reputation foster a sense of security and comfort among patients, which in turn encourages them to revisit the hospital. Therefore, strengthening brand image is a crucial strategy for building long-term patient loyalty.

The Effect of Trust on Revisit Intention

Trust is proven to have a positive and significant effect on patients' revisit intention. This result indicates that the higher the level of patient trust in the hospital, medical staff, and service procedures, the stronger the intention to return for future treatment. Trust creates confidence that the hospital is capable of delivering safe, reliable, and appropriate healthcare services in accordance with patient expectations. Moreover, trust serves as an emotional factor that reinforces long-term relationships between patients and the hospital. When patients perceive that they are treated professionally, transparently, and responsibly, they are more likely to overlook potential risks and uncertainties in healthcare services. This condition fosters patient loyalty, which is reflected in an increased intention to revisit the hospital.

The Effect of Service Quality on Revisit Intention

The findings of this study show that service quality has a positive and significant effect on patients' revisit intention. This confirms that high-quality services, such as timely service delivery, staff friendliness, clear medical information, and adequate facilities, create positive experiences for patients. These experiences become key considerations in patients' decisions to revisit the hospital. In addition, high service quality reflects the hospital's commitment to meeting patient needs and expectations. Responsive, empathetic, and professional services not only

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enhance patient satisfaction but also strengthen patients' willingness to establish long-term relationships with the hospital. Therefore, continuous improvement of service quality is a strategic factor in increasing patients' revisit intention.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of this study, it can be concluded that brand image, trust, and service quality have positive and significant effects on patients' revisit intention, both directly and indirectly through patient satisfaction. A strong hospital brand image is able to create positive perceptions and confidence among patients, which encourages them to choose the same hospital for future healthcare services. Trust in the hospital, medical personnel, and service procedures also plays a crucial role in strengthening patients' intention to revisit, as it provides a sense of security and reliability in receiving medical treatment. Furthermore, service quality is identified as a dominant factor influencing patient satisfaction and revisit intention. High-quality services that are reliable, responsive, and empathetic significantly enhance patient satisfaction, which in turn reinforces patients' loyalty and willingness to return. Patient satisfaction acts as an important mediating variable that amplifies the influence of brand image, trust, and service quality on revisit intention. Overall, these findings highlight the importance for hospitals to consistently improve service quality, maintain a positive brand image, and build patient trust in order to enhance satisfaction and sustain long-term patient loyalty.

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